

MODERN FACTORS OF ELIMINATION OF DISORDER ARISING AT CITY INTERSECTIONS AND INTERSECTIONS

Abdurahmonov Adxamjon

Senior lecturer, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute

Sahodullaev Asror

Student, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute

Toshtemirov Shahbos

Student, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute

Sodiqjonov Murodjon

Student, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute

Abstract: this article focuses on the modern factors of eliminating the disturbances that arise at city intersections and intersections in our country, as well as the current problems of ensuring the safety of the population.

Key words: regulated and unregulated intersections, roads, traffic lights, rail and non-rail vehicles.

In recent years, extensive organizational and practical work has been carried out in the field of improving the road safety system in our country. In particular, in order to prevent disturbances at city intersections and crossings in our country, first of all, it is necessary to strictly follow the traffic rules. This, in turn, helps ensure the safety of road users. The providers of such safety are traffic safety officers, traffic lights and intersections.

An intersection is a place where roads cross, join and diverge at the same level, where traffic may or may not be regulated.

If the order of traffic at the intersection is defined by a traffic light or regulator as regulated intersections, such an intersection is considered a regulated intersection. At regulated intersections, the driver of non-rail vehicles turning left or turning on

the green signal of the traffic light must give way to vehicles moving straight and turning right from the opposite side. If we act on the basis of this rule, we will be able to partially eliminate the unpleasant incidents that occur on the road. Tram drivers must also follow this rule.

Another example of this is that when the traffic light is on, the driver must give way to vehicles completing the movement through the intersection and to pedestrians completing the passage in the appropriate direction.

Irregular intersections are defined as priority signs at intersections of densely trafficked and non-trafficked roads, in the absence of which the drivers themselves determine whether there is a mutual path, the right and right of the vehicle approaching the intersection. depending on the location on the left side.

At unregulated intersections, at the intersection of roads of equal importance, regardless of the direction of traffic, the vehicle coming from the main road must give way to the driver of the vehicle coming from the secondary road. At the intersection of roads of equal importance, the driver of a non-rail vehicle must give way to vehicles coming from the right.

Tram drivers must also follow these rules. At such intersections, regardless of the direction of traffic, the tram has the right of way over non-rail vehicles. By following these rules, we can safely cross the intersections.

One more thing we can say as information is that it is necessary to make traffic at intersections the right way. In this case, the driver turning left or right must give way to pedestrians crossing the road, as well as cyclists crossing the road from the bicycle lane.

Based on these rules, drivers must strictly follow all of the above. This helps to ensure the safety of pedestrians.

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